

Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05)

**A.E. Bras
V.H.J. van der Velden**

Laboratory Medical Immunology (LMI), Department of Immunology, Erasmus Medical Center, Erasmus University, Rotterdam, the Netherlands
Correspondence: a.e.bras@gmail.com / a.bras@erasmusmc.nl / v.h.j.vandervelden@erasmusmc.nl

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.2559524

License

Creative Commons - Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published five papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵
06-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰

Note

Previously, authors used ‘CSR’ to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to natural numbers (as originally introduced by Inder Taneja) and ‘NCSR’ to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to negative integers (as introduced by ourselves). Authors always avoided ‘PCSR’ as this might introduce ambiguity (pseudo vs. positive CSR).

From this point forward, authors will use the following:

- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any integer value
- +CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any positive integer
- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any negative integer

Historic Overview Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^6+7_{11}*89_A$		$A9_{11}^{(8_{11}-7_{11})}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^6+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{(8_{12}-7_{12})}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^6+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{(8_{13}-7_{13})}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^6+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{(8_{14}-7_{14})}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^6+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{(8_{15}-7_{15})}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^6+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{(8_{16}-7_{16})}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 10 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 + - * / ^ ()

Digits 1 up to 9 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45^*(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^*(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(-(1+2)+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9)))$	$-((9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Attempt to ‘fill the gaps’ in our previous work ^{6,7,8,12,13,14,15,25,30} by identifying...

- increasing genuine CSR for integers without any increasing genuine CSR.
- decreasing genuine CSR for integers without any decreasing genuine CSR.

Results

Authors identified 16488 previously unknown genuine CSR, see supplements.

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	2390	5425	2306	6367

Overview

Currently, within the -2147483647 up to 2147483647 range, increasing CSR are available for 1752072 integers, and decreasing CSR are available for 2441622 integers:

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	873978	1220568	870593	1197268
Pseudo	2103	420	5398	23366
Total	876081	1220988	875991	1220634

Note

Authors consider CSR to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published CSR are the shortest in existence.
- Published CSR are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable CSR do not exists.

References

1. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v1>
Natural Numbers from 44 to 1000 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 6 Feb 2013.
2. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v2>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 44 to 4444 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Tuesday 19 Mar 2013
3. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v3>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 1 to 11111 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 5 Jun 2013
4. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v4>
More on Crazy Sequential Representation of Natural Numbers with Subtraction
Inder J. Taneja. Monday 5 Aug 2013
5. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v5>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 0 to 11111 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 8 Jan 2014
6. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6483968>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1288822>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Tuesday 12 Jun 2018
7. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6516131>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1288892>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Thursday 14 Jun 2018
8. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6587117>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1292115>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Jun 2018
9. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a108.pdf>
MD5: BB89800FB86BDF830D28EB07241D78C1
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 12 Sep 2018

10. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a131.pdf>
MD5: D135C0F9A417B7221AEBB1225FDF7B8D
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000
Inder J. Taneja. Saturday 10 Nov 2018
11. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a132.pdf>
MD5: 87BF426B1827555F5FB701F7DAE33969
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000
Inder J. Taneja. Saturday 10 Nov 2018
12. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7429967>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1998118>
Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Thursday 06 Dec 2018
13. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7467665>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2276623>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 14 Dec 2018
14. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7505690>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2525823>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 24 Dec 2018
15. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7539311>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530025>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 02 Jan 2019
16. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.05070v1>
Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases
Tim Wylie. Thursday 11 Oct 2018
17. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546955>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530974>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
18. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546958>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530976>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
19. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546970>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530978>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019

20. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546982>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530980>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
21. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546985>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530982>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
22. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546991>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530984>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
23. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7564973>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2536047>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 09 Jan 2019
24. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7547423>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.2531777>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFFF)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
25. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7639799>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551565>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 28 Jan 2019
26. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7619648>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2547763>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to ####)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 23 Jan 2019
27. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7665629>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555620>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to ####)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Saturday 02 Feb 2019
28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2543626>
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000
Inder J. Taneja. Monday 18 Jan 2019
29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2556036>
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000
Inder J. Taneja. Sunday 03 Feb 2019

30. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7683572>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2558454>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 06 Feb 2019